

Study protocols

Collaboration on Rare Diseases as part of the Medical Informatics Initiative (CORD-MI)

Disclaimer

*This is an excerpt from the original study protocol (as of December 21, 2020)
which was created as part of CORD-MI.*

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Table of contents

Table of contents.....	2
Scientists involved.....	3
Coordination of the joint project CORD-MI.....	5
Steering Committee CORD-MI.....	5
Financing.....	5
Background.....	6
Cystic fibrosis (CF).....	6
Questions.....	7
Primary Question.....	7
Secondary Questions.....	7
Study-related measures / course of study.....	8
Clarification.....	8
Data protection concept.....	8
Effect / Benefit.....	9
Burden / risks.....	9
Accompanying therapy.....	9
Methodology.....	9
Required data from the DIC.....	9
Study type.....	10
Inclusion criteria.....	10
Exclusion criteria.....	10
Safety laboratory.....	10
Termination criteria.....	11
Randomization procedure / plan.....	11
Statistical analysis.....	11
Local data analysis.....	11
Merging the data.....	11
Central data evaluation.....	11
Data protection / data flow / collection and handling of clinical data.....	11
Flow chart incl. schedule.....	13
Reporting / Publications.....	14
Ethical and legal aspects.....	14
References.....	15

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Financing

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<https://www.medizininformatik-initiative.de/de/CORD>

Background

In the project "Collaboration on Rare Diseases (CORD-MI)" of the German Medical Informatics Initiative (MII) founded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research, twenty German university hospitals and other partners are committed to improving care and research in the field of rare diseases. The MII is based on the action plan of the National Action Alliance for People with Rare Diseases (German "Nationales Aktionsbündnis für Menschen mit Seltenen Erkrankungen; NAMSE), whose founding members are ACHSE e.V., the German Federal Ministry of Health and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. Each of the university hospitals in CORD-MI has a Center for Rare Diseases, is a member of one of the four MII consortia (HiGHmed / DIFUTURE / MIRACUM / SMITH) and is at an advanced stage of establishing a Data Integration and Competence Center (DIC) according to the rules of the MII.

CORD-MI uses the organizational and technical solutions of the MII with the aim of improving care and research in the field of rare diseases. Data from 20 university hospitals, which will be available via the DIC, will be jointly analyzed. The aim is to prove that the IT solutions developed in the project and by the MII consortia lead to measurable benefits for patients, doctors and researchers. Furthermore, CORD-MI contributes to the overall outcome of the MII, for example by expanding medical documentation and testing innovative approaches to linking and evaluating data.

On the clinical side, CORD-MI aims to increase the visibility of rare diseases, provide insights into the reality of care, stimulate research in this area as well as evaluate and improve the quality of diagnostic and therapeutic processes. The CORD-MI project is intended to produce structures, processes and results that promote the care of people with rare diseases and research in this field locally, nationally and internationally. For the first time, data on rare diseases will be collected systematically, uniformly and interoperable in a large number of German university hospitals.

On the medical informatics side, CORD-MI focuses on improving concepts and solutions for the clinical documentation of rare diseases, on organizational, semantic and syntactic interoperability and on data protection-compliant methods for nationwide data access. With this in mind, CORD-MI is piloting and evaluating a number of solutions and then developing proposals for improvement that will be made available to a larger national and international community.

The project sees itself as a learning system. It works step by step and builds on the continuous progress of the MII. Furthermore, it is developing its own management cycle in which lessons are learned from the previous steps for the subsequent ones. This applies to documentation development, data usage concepts and data protection methods. It should be possible to make fundamental use of the results in the healthcare context and subsequent research projects, as well as to develop the concepts, methods and technologies in a subsequent phase of the MII.

In the following, the clinical picture of Cystic Fibrosis (CF) and the relevant clinical questions as well as the necessary methodological and data-technical procedure are described.

Cystic fibrosis (CF)

CF is a congenital multi-organ disease. It is caused by a defect in the so-called CFTR gene, which regulates salt and fluid transport through epithelial cells. CF is one of the rare diseases affecting around 8,000 patients in Germany. The incidence in newborns in Germany is 1 : 3,300 to 1 : 4,800 [1]. In recent years, significant improvements in health and life expectancy have been achieved. Previously predominantly a childhood disease, there are now more adults than children living with cystic fibrosis in Germany. As a result, there is an increase in the number of women with CF are becoming pregnant,

although this is associated with an higher risk for the pregnant woman and the child [2]. It is therefore recommended that care during pregnancy and delivery takes place in a specialized center. In Germany, around 50 pregnancies are expected per year. The German Cystic Fibrosis Registry is a good source of data, in which medical data from around 6,100 patients from 91 CF facilities have been documented for over 20 years (www.muko.info).

Questions

Various aspects of the quality of care for CF are to be investigated.

Primary Question

What is the proportion of pregnant women with CF who gave birth in a CF center between 2015 and 2021?

According to the guideline, all patients with CF should give birth in a specialized center. However, it is reported that this is not always the case. Therefore, the number of births determined by the DIC at the respective university hospital (source (1)) should be compared with the number of births reported by the attending physicians at the hospital (source (2)).

If cumulative data from all centers are available, these can also be compared with the cumulative data from the German Cystic Fibrosis Registry (source (3)).

Secondary Questions

The data from the DIC of the participating university hospitals form the basis for the analysis within the framework of CORD-MI. Their data stock is based on routine data. The quality of these data sets for research questions is limited. The question therefore arises as to whether reliable results can also be achieved for rare diseases using this data source.

[A] *How high is the data quality in the DIC for rare diseases?*

The clinical picture of CF was chosen as the first disease entity because, in addition to the data from the local DIC other data sources can be used to examine the quality of the data for the primary research question. These are

- (1) the attending physicians in the CF centers of the respective university hospital on the basis of their documents, memories and entries in the Cystic Fibrosis Registry
- (2) the German Cystic Fibrosis Registry.

Re (1): The aim is to investigate whether the number of births determined by the respective DIC corresponds to the number of births determined by the total number of pregnancies of patients with CF treated at the center (difference as a percentage of the number determined by the physician). If a difference is observed, the underlying causes should be described (birth not at the center, documentation error, technical problem).

Re (2): Does the sum of the cumulative birth numbers determined from the participating DIC correspond to the births documented in the German Cystic Fibrosis Registry for the participating centers in 2015-2021?

[B] How often do complications occur during pregnancy and delivery?

The respective frequencies of combinations of the diagnosis code E84.x for CF with a code for birth (e.g. O80) and one of the ICD codes listed in Table 1 for a complication (e.g. gestational diabetes - O24.4) are to be determined (e.g. number of E84.x AND (O80 or O81 or O82 or O30.x) AND O24.4). There is only one AND link between birth in a person with CF and a complication.

[C] Which child outcomes can be observed?

The following Table 2 and Table 3 (gestational age, birth weight, length and head circumference of the child) in combination with ICD E84.x of the mother. The variables in the table are not linked to each other.

The study is based on data from the perinatal survey for the years 2015 to 2021.

The frequencies determined for [B] and [C] should be set in relation to German reference data, including health reporting.

Since the current core dataset of the MII, which must be available at the DIC, does not (yet) provide for linking the datasets of a birthing mother with her newborn child and information such as gestational age of the child, birth weight, length and head circumference are also not (yet) part of the core dataset, the secondary question [C] can only be processed by some centers.

Study-related measures / course of study

As existing data records are evaluated, there are no additional measures or increased time expenditure for patients.

The study described here is a retrospective cross-sectional survey of the years 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021, based exclusively on data already collected. All patients who can be identified in the local DIC on the basis of the ICD codes described above are included. The analyses are carried out in the same way in all participating university hospitals. The results are initially evaluated locally. If there is a data protection-compliant solution in place (see below) and after renewed consultation with the local ethics committees (amendment), it is planned to merge the data centrally in the sense of a multicenter design.

Clarification

In this study, the data is extracted without obtaining consent, so there is no informed consent process.

Data protection concept

The names of patients and all other confidential information are subject to medical confidentiality, the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the provisions of the State/Federal Data Protection Act (LDSG/BDSG).

In general, the study data is anonymized as soon as this is possible according to the research purpose. Only anonymized data is merged across the participating sites.

If study results are published, patient data is also published anonymously.

The source data is only accessible to the study team. All data will be stored without further notice for up to 10 years after the end of the project.

Effect / Benefit

This study will have no impact on the patients' diseases. There will be no direct personal benefit for the individual patients, but the study should lead to a better understanding of the diseases, which could also be of benefit to individual patients in the future.

Burden / risks

As only anonymized data is evaluated retrospectively as part of this study, there is neither a burden nor a risk for the patients as a result of the study. As a rule, patients will not be aware of the evaluation of their data as part of this study.

Accompanying therapy

The study has no influence on the therapy / concomitant therapy of the patients.

Methodology

Required data from the DIC

The sub-project on CF is based on data that is available in ICD-10-GM-coded form or was recorded as part of the neonatal survey. For the evaluations, the data for the years 2015 - 2021 are recorded separately for each year and also cumulatively for all five years.

In the case of CF, a case-related evaluation of the data of hospitalized women with CF is carried out. In a first step, the cases are identified at each location in which a birth (O80, O81 or O82) was coded in addition to the diagnosis of cystic fibrosis (E84.x). Further ICD-10GM codes to be evaluated, which primarily reflect maternal complications associated with pregnancy and delivery in CF, are listed in the following Table 1.

Table 1. ICD codes included in the analysis for patients with CF

	ICD-10-GM code	Description
Mother	O80	Spontaneous delivery of a singleton
Mother	O81	Birth of a singleton by forceps or vacuum extraction
Mother	O82	Birth of a singleton by incisional delivery
Mother	Z37.x	Result of the delivery
Mother	O30.x	Multiple pregnancy
Mother	Z38.x	Live births by place of birth
Mother	O64.x	Obstacle to birth
Mother	O09.x	Duration of pregnancy
Mother	O75.x	Other complications during labor and delivery
Mother	O24.4	Diabetes during pregnancy
Mother	J18.x	Pneumonia, unspecified
Mother	O63	Protract birth

Table 2. Additional data included in the analysis for the identified mothers with CF

Age	< 18 years, 18 ... < 31 years, ≥ 31 years
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The following Table 2 and Table 3 summarize the additional data that can only be provided by DIC at some locations.

Table 3. ICD codes included in the analysis for newborns of patients with CF

Child data that can be assigned to the mother data:		
Child(ren)	P05.x	Intrauterine deficiency development and fetal malnutrition
Child(ren)	P07.x	Disorders associated with short duration of pregnancy and low birth weight
Child(ren)	P95	Fetal death of unspecified cause

Table 4. Additional data included in the analysis for newborns of patients with CF

Child data to be optionally assigned to the mother data:		
Child(ren)	Gestational age	categorical (20th - 25th week of pregnancy, 26th - 33rd week of pregnancy, 34th - 36th week of pregnancy, 37th - 41st week of pregnancy,
Child(ren)	Birth weight of the child	categorical: 500 - 749g, 750 - 999g, 1000 - 1249g, 1225 - 1499g, 1500 - 1999g, 2000 - 2499g, 2500 - 2999g, 3000 - 3999g, 4000 - 4499g, ≥ 4500g
Child(ren)	Length of the child	categorical: < 40cm, 40 - < 45cm, 45 - < 50cm, 50 - < 55cm, ≥ 55cm
Child(ren)	Head circumference of the child	categorical: < 31cm, 31 - < 33cm, 33 - < 35cm, 35 - < 37cm, ≥ 37cm

Study type

This is an open, uncontrolled, non-randomized, national, multicenter study.

Inclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria defined for the study are:

- Confirmed diagnosis of CF.
- No age restriction.

Exclusion criteria

None

Safety laboratory

Not required

Termination criteria

- Individual: None
- Entire study: None

Randomization procedure / plan

There is no randomization in this study.

Statistical analysis

A purely descriptive description of the variables listed above and their simple AND linkage in the form of frequencies or proportions is provided. In addition, the project evaluates the MII instruments by determining the completeness and data quality of the data available in the DIC.

Due to the purely descriptive approach, there is no biometric justification for the number of cases.

Local data analysis

The results are initially evaluated locally at each participating location. For the joint analysis, the data must be available in the form of frequencies (number). For this purpose, the continuously distributed variables birth weight, gestational age, etc. are categorized (e.g. birth weight < 1500g, 1501 - 2,500g, etc.) and the frequency in each category is determined.

Merging the data

Only anonymized data is merged across the participating locations.

Since there can also be very low frequencies (<5) at a location, individual patients could lead to the identifiability of individual persons if the numbers of each location were transferred directly to a common database.

If the research question allows, groups containing less than 5 individuals can be combined with appropriate groups containing $n > 5$ individuals (forming groups of ICD codes or not stratified by age or sex).

If such a solution is not possible due to the issue at hand, the data will be merged. A data protection-compliant solution will be developed on the basis of the knowledge gained locally and submitted subsequently. Until then, the data will only be analyzed locally at the participating locations.

Central data evaluation

For the purpose of this study, the data is to be imported locally into a standardized evaluation database in pseudonymized form at each location. The data elements used are described in

Data protection / data flow / collection and handling of clinical data

Data management in the data integration centers of the MII follows defined and standardized processes, which are set out in principle in the applicable data protection concepts and procedural rules of the respective consortium and locations.

The initial data use and data protection concept of the CORD-MI joint project in the version dated May 24, 2020, on which the TMF e.V. data protection working group issued a positive statement on May 30, 2020, is aligned with this. For the set-up phase of CORD-MI, the concept provides for a restriction to so-called “decentralized analyses”, whose aggregated local partial results are only merged centrally if they do not allow conclusions to be drawn about individual patients.

For the study, CORD-MIÄs data use and data protection concept provides for the following for each question in turn

(1a) Local preparations in the DIC (= provision of MII core data set),

(1b) provision of frequencies from other data sources (e.g. German Cystic Fibrosis Registry, PIMS Survey) to check data quality,

(2a) an iterative creation of central scripts taking into account the results of the local data quality check results,

(2b) the controlled execution of the centrally created scripts at all locations (= controlled remote data processing of the MII core data set), with local retention of the results, and

(3) provided that a data protection-compliant solution is available (see above): Central meta-analyses by merging the decentralized (partial) results

before.

Re (1): The local preparations for the core dataset (1a) are congruent with the data preparation already underway in the MII to provide the basic data in the format of the MII core dataset. The collection of data from routine care takes place independently of the MII processes (1b). The legal basis at most locations is the respective state hospital law, which allows hospitals in general or university hospitals in particular to conduct their own research with patient data from the care context. Data use and data protection concepts as well as organizational and technical measures must be guaranteed at all locations. Clarification and facilitation must take place locally. The participating sites are provided with (i) a CORD-MI sample entry for the local processing directory and (ii) a sample data protection impact assessment.

Regarding (2): Controlled remote data processing means that a cooperative task force creates a script for each question using data structure files, which is executed locally at all locations remotely from the task force. The anonymity of the aggregated results must also be checked at the site. No legal basis is required for the creation of the scripts. For the decentralized execution of the scripts and the examination of the (partial) results, the basis for permission must be clarified by the locations with the local data protection officers in the sense of in-house research (as 1.). The participating locations are provided with (i) a CORD-MI sample entry for the local processing directory and (ii) a sample data protection impact assessment.

Re (3): The local (partial) results are aggregated, anonymous figures with no direct patient reference. The local results at the locations are used to check whether the data is anonymous and can therefore be merged without further measures. If there is a data protection-compliant solution is available (see above) and after renewed consultation (a corresponding amendment) by the local ethics committees, the data will then be merged centrally. The participating locations will be provided with (i) a CORD-MI sample entry for the local processing directory and (ii) a sample data protection impact assessment.

Flow chart incl. schedule

The course of the project over the 24-month term starting in February 2020 is shown in Figure 1.

Aufgabenliste und Zeitplan		2020	2021	2022	
WP1	Studienprotokoll, Ethik, Datenschutz				
T1.1	Iterative Entwicklung von Studienprotokollen für die CORD-Beobachtungsstudien				
	T1.1.1 Protokoll für die Studie über Mukoviszidose	D1.1.1			
	T1.1.2 Protokoll zur Studie über Phenylketonurie	D1.1.2			
	T1.1.3 Protokoll für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D1.1.3			
	T1.1.4 Protokoll zur Untersuchung der isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D1.1.4		
	T1.1.5 Protokoll zur Untersuchung des POMC-Mangels			D1.1.5	
	T1.1.6 Protokoll für die Großpflegeüberwachung		D1.1.6		
T1.2	Iterative Entwicklung von Datenschutzkonzepten für die CORD-Beobachtungsstudien				
	T1.2.1 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur Mukoviszidose	D1.2.1			
	T1.2.2 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie	D1.2.2			
	T1.2.3 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D1.2.3			
	T1.2.4 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D1.2.4		
	T1.2.5 Datenschutzkonzept für die Studie zum POMC-Mangel			D1.2.5	
	T1.2.6 Datenschutzkonzept für die großflächige Pflegeüberwachung		D1.2.6		
T1.3	Ethikgenehmigung für Studien und Veröffentlichung von Protokollen				
	T1.3.1 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über Mukoviszidose genehmigt und Registrierung	D1.3.1			
	T1.3.2 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über Phenylketonurie genehmigt und Registrierung	D1.3.2			
	T1.3.3 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry genehmigt und Registrierung		D1.3.3		
	T1.3.4 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über isolierte sagittale Nahtsynostose genehmigt und			D1.3.4	
	T1.3.5 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Studie über den POMC-Mangel genehmigt und Registrierung				D1.3.5
	T1.3.6 Überprüfung des Protokolls für die Überwachung der Großversorgung genehmigt und Registrierung			D1.3.6	
WP2	Dokumentationssupport				
	T2.1 Formale Spezifikation für Codierwerkzeuge (ID DIACOS, 3M KODIP) und seine Integration (Agfa ORBIS, CERNER i.s.h.med, CERNER Medico, MEONA Meona, SAP IS/H)	D2.1			
	T2.2 Seine Integration (Agfa ORBIS, CERNER i.s.h.med, CERNER Medico, MEONA Meona, SAP IS/H)	D2.2			
	T2.3 Technische Lösung an den Standorten implementiert	D2.3			
	T2.4 Installierte klinische Prozesse und vollständige Dokumentation für Orpha-Nummern und Alpha-ID-		D2.4		
WP3	Datenintegration				
T3.1	Erweiterung der Module				
	T3.1.1 Erweiterung des Moduls "Fall".	D3.1.1			
	T3.1.2 Erweiterung des Moduls "Diagnose".		D3.1.2		
	T3.1.3 Erweiterungsmodul " Symptome "		D3.1.3		
	T3.1.4 Erweiterungsmodul " Genealogie "			D3.1.4	
T3.2	Datenextraktions- und Integrations-Pipelines				
	T3.2.1 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über Mukoviszidose	D3.2.1			
	T3.2.2 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über Phenylketonurie	D3.2.2			
	T3.2.3 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit	D3.2.3			
	T3.2.4 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose		D3.2.4		
	T3.2.5 Datenextraktions- und Integrationspipelines für die Studie über POMC-Mangel			D3.2.5	
T3.3	Datenbereitstellung				
	T3.3.1 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über Mukoviszidose	D3.3.1			
	T3.3.2 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über Phenylketonurie	D3.3.2			
	T3.3.3 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit		D3.3.3		
	T3.3.4 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose			D3.3.4	
	T3.3.5 Datenbereitstellungspipeline für die Studie über POMC-Mangel				D3.3.5
WP4	Überwachung der Datenqualität				
	T4.1 Definition von Datenqualitätskennzahlen und Berichten	D4.1			
	T4.2 Halbjährliche Datenqualitätsberichte für die Datenerhebung		D4.2	D4.2	D4.2
	T4.3 Vierteljährliche Datenqualitätsberichte zur Datenqualität der Integration und Bereitstellung	D4.3	D4.3	D4.3	D4.3
	T4.4 interkonsortiales Dashboard für die Datenqualität		D4.4		
WP5	Datenanalyse				
TS.1	Definition der Datenanalyse				
	TS.1.1.1 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Mukoviszidose	D5.1.1			
	TS.1.1.2 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie	D5.1.2			
	TS.1.1.3 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit		D5.1.3		
	TS.1.1.4 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose			D5.1.4	
	TS.1.1.5 Definition der standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie über POMC-Mangel				D5.1.5
TS.2	Implementierung der Datenanalyse				
	TS.2.1 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Mukoviszidose	D5.2.1			
	TS.2.2 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie	D5.2.2			
	TS.2.3 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur Morbus Fabry.		D5.2.3		
	TS.2.4 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen			D5.2.4	
	TS.2.5 Durchführung einer standortübergreifenden Analyse für die Studie zum POMC-Mangel				D5.2.5
	TS.3 Implementierung einer konsortialübergreifenden Analyseplattform				D5.3
TS.4	Datenanalyse-Ergebnisse				
	TS.4.1 Interkonsortialanalyse für die Studie über Mukoviszidose				D5.4.1
	TS.4.2 Cross-Konsortialanalyse für die Studie zur Phenylketonurie				D5.4.2
	TS.4.3 Interkonsortialanalyse für die Studie über die Morbus Fabry-Krankheit				D5.4.3
	TS.4.4 Cross-Konsortialanalyse für die Studie zur isolierten sagittalen Nahtsynostose				D5.4.4
	TS.4.5 Cross-Konsortialanalyse für die Studie über POMC-Mangel				D5.4.5
WP6	Rollout und Verbreitung der Ergebnisse				
	T6.1 Entwicklung eines Vertriebskonzepts für Softwaremodule		D6.1		
	T6.2 Entwicklung einer Projekt-Website im laufenden Betrieb			D6.2	
	T6.3 Organisation eines wissenschaftlichen Symposiums		D6.3		
	T6.4 Veröffentlichung der geografischen Verteilung der RD im seAtlas			D6.4	
WP7	Projektleitung				
	T7.1 Entwicklung einer Kollaborationsplattform	D7.1			
	T7.2 Entwicklung einer Kooperationsstruktur	D7.2			
	T7.3 Halbjährliche Fortschrittsberichte für das NSG	D7.3	D7.3	D7.3	D7.3

Figure 1. Gantt chart illustrating the work packages over the project duration including milestones

Reporting / Publications

All data collected is used exclusively for scientific purposes.

The findings from this research project should provide clarity about the usability of the technical and organizational possibilities of MII for care and research in the field of rare diseases. In addition, proof is to be provided that cross-consortia technical solutions for data use in the context of MII can be made available. It is planned to present these to a broad readership in scientific journals in the near future.

CORD-MI aims to increase the visibility of rare diseases, provide insights into the reality of care, stimulate research in this field and evaluate and improve the quality of current diagnostic and therapeutic processes. For this reason, the clinical results are also to be published in scientific journals exclusively in anonymized form. This ensures that it is not possible to re-identify individual patients with rare diseases. Only percentages or k-anonymized frequencies will be published.

Ethical and legal aspects

The planning, implementation and use of the project and the project results will be in accordance with the relevant ethical and scientific standards. The applicants thus undertake to comply with the requirements of the Memorandum on Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice of the German Research Foundation (DFG), the Declaration of Helsinki and Memorandum III "Methods for Health Services Research" of the German Network for Health Services Research, the State and Federal Data Protection Act and the General Data Protection Regulation of the European Union (EU GDPR) and the respective applicable state hospital laws in their current versions. In addition, the clinically active colleagues involved follow the professional regulations for doctors of the relevant state medical association in the current versions.

The study plan is submitted to the Ethics Committee (EC) of the University of Würzburg, appointed in accordance with state law, for consultation before the start of the study program. Once the vote of the first advisory committee is available, the votes of the local ethics committees of the participating locations are obtained. Data analysis will not begin until the written, approving vote of the ethics committees of all participating sites has been received.

The names of the patients and all other confidential information for the provision of frequencies from other data sources for data quality checks are subject to the medical confidentiality of the treating physicians and the provisions of the General Data Protection Regulation and the Federal Data Protection Acts (GDPR and BDSG new) as well as the state data protection laws of the respective federal states.

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